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UTERINE MUCOSAL MORPHOLOGY OF INTRAUTERINE CONTRACEPTIVE USE (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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ANNOTATION

Intrauterine devices are one of the most popular and effective methods of contraception, but their safety is still being studied by scientists. Possible adverse effects of this method of contraception are fibroblastic transformation of the stroma, non-specific chronic endometritis, atrophy of the endometrium at the sites of contact with the contraceptive, hyperplastic changes of the uterine body, especially of the mucosa, and the presence of "inflammatory" infiltrates in the endometrium. All of these are biological reactions of the organism to a foreign body. Structural and functional changes of the uterine cervix deserve separate attention.

Key words: intrauterine contraception, complications of intrauterine contraception, chronic endometritis, endometrial hyperplasia, cervical polyps, endometrial fibrosis.

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МОРФОЛОГИЯ СЛИЗИСТОЙ ОБОЛОЧКИ МАТКИ ПРИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИИ ВНУТРИМАТОЧНЫХ ПРОТИВОЗАЧАТОЧНЫХ СРЕДСТВ (ОБЗОР ЛИТЕРАТУРЫ)

АННОТАЦИЯ

Внутриматочные устройства являются одним из самых популярных и эффективных способов контрацепции, однако их безопасность до сих пор изучается учеными. Возможными негативными последствиями применения данного способа контрацепции являются фибробластическая трансформация стромы, неспецифический хронический эндометрит, атрофия эндометрия в местах контакта с контрацептивом, гиперпластические изменения тела

матки, в особенности слизистой оболочки, и наличие «воспалительных» инфильтратов в эндометрии. Все это является биологической реакцией организма на инородное тело. Отдельного внимания стоят структурно-функциональные изменения шейки матки.

Ключевые слова: внутриматочная контрацепция, осложнения внутриматочной контрацепции, хронический эндометрит, гиперплазия эндометрия, полипы шейки матки, фиброз эндометрия.

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BACHADON ICHI KONTRATSEPTIV VOSITALARDAN FOYDALANGANDA BACHADON SHILLIQ QAVATINING MORFOLOGIYASI (ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI)

ANNOTATSIYA

Bachadon ichi kontratseptiv vositalari mashhur va samarali usullaridan biridir, ammo ularning xavfsizligi hali ham olimlar tomonidan o'rganilmoqda. Ushbu kontratseptsiya usulini qo'llashning mumkin bo'lgan salbiy oqibatlari stromaning fibroblastik transformatsiyasi, o'ziga xos bo'lmagan surunkali endometrit, kontratseptiv vositalar bilan aloqa qilish joylarida endometrium atrofiyasi, bachadon tanasidagi giperplastik o'zgarishlar, ayniqsa shilliq qavat va endometriumda "yallig'lanish" infiltratlarining mavjudligi. Bularning barchasi organizmning begona jismga biologik reaksiyasidir. Serviksdagi tarkibiy va funktsional o'zgarishlarga alohida e'tibor beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: bachadon ichi kontratseptsiyasi, kontratseptsiya, intrauterin kontratseptsiya asoratlari, surunkali endometrit, Endometriyal giperplaziya, bachadon bo'yni polioplari, Endometriyal fibroz.

Relevance. The introduction into widespread practice of the most effective, harmless, long-acting contraceptives is of great social and medical importance for the health of mothers and future offspring [1]. Intrauterine contraceptives are one of the most common methods of contraception, with tens of millions of women worldwide using them [2,12]. Histological study of biopsied endometrium is objective evidence of the nature and depth of the effect of intrauterine contraceptives on the uterine mucosa [6]. Some researchers in 78-92 % of observations did not reveal any abnormalities in the endometrium when using intrauterine contraceptives (IUDs). A number of authors [8] found that the presence of IUD in the uterine cavity leads to a disruption in the timing of its maturation. Inconsistency of structural changes in the uterine mucosa to the day of the menstrual cycle is manifested as a lag in its morphofunctional development or as an acceleration of the functional activity of the endometrium, which leads to premature secretory transformations of its . There are also indications of asynchronism of transformations of glands and endometrial stroma. M. Sammour et al. [4] noted a delay in the secretory phase of the cycle more often - in 41.7%, other researchers found that 11.9% of women with IUDs have a delay in the secretory phase of the menstrual cycle, and 9.1% - its early onset. C. Shang et al[3] diagnosed a predecidual reaction in the uterine body mucosa both in clinical observations (3 %) and in experimental studies.

It was found that the lag of endometrial structural transformation depended to some extent on the day of the menstrual cycle in which the study was conducted. It was least pronounced in the endometrium studied on the 17th - 19th day of the cycle, in the following days its severity increased: the greatest lag of structural transformations was observed in the endometrium obtained 2 days before menstruation. These changes did not depend on the duration of IUD wear and the time of IUD insertion (immediately after abortion or outside of it) [2]. Disturbances in the histophysiological properties of the endometrium were observed not only in the areas of contact of the uterine mucosa with the contraceptive, but also in other parts of the uterus. A similar relationship in the maturation of the endometrium was established by W. Bo et al. [7], who tend to explain this mechanism of the

contraceptive effect of the IUD. These changes are reversible, as evidenced by their absence in the endometrium biopsied 2.5 - 4 months after the removal of the contraceptive.

Fibrosis of the stroma in the superficial layers of some parts of the endometrium, fragments of fibrous tissue are observed in 1.6 - 5.8% of women using intrauterine contraceptives [8]. The incidence of stromal fibrosis increased with increasing duration of pessary wear [3]. J. Rejniak et al [4] in clinical observations in women who had been given IUDs immediately after abortion, and A. David et al. [3,6] in experimental studies on rabbits showed that endometrial regeneration in the presence of IUD is 3 to 4 times slower than without it. Around the intrauterine contraceptive the authors observed an acute inflammatory process, and later the formation of fibrous tissue. O.K.Khmelnitsky [10] notes that after the disappearance of inflammation in this place is formed fibrosis of its own layer of the endometrium or yfibroadenomatous micropolyposis of the endometrium. Separate attention should be paid to the so-called "inflammatory" infiltrates of the endometrium, determined in 8 - 27% of cases, which are accompanied by clinical symptoms only in 3.5 - 19% of observations.

D. Moueg et al. [11] indicate a correlation between the period of IUD placement in the uterine cavity and the nature of endometrial cell infiltration. First of all, after IUD insertion, neutrophilic leukocytes and mononuclear cells (lymphocytes and monocytes) were detected in the stroma of the uterine mucosa, then during 45-50 days the number of cellular elements increased, especially in the places of contact between the contraceptive and the endometrium. From day 50 to 201, 1/3 of the observations showed infiltration with mononuclear cells. No significant plasma cell infiltration was observed in any case. The researchers especially emphasise this point, since the presence of plasma cells is a characteristic feature of chronic endometrium, according to a number of authors [13]. Одни исследователи считают, что указанную инфильтрацию следует рассматривать как асептическое воспаление [3,7], другие оценивают ее как проявление инфекционного эндометрита [4]. It is known, however, that single lymphocytes and segmented leukocytes can also be found in the endometrium of healthy women [8] who do not use IUDs, so their presence does not indicate chronic infection. The absence in most cases of clinical manifestations characteristic of chronic endometritis also argues against the latter. This is evidenced by the fact that such infiltrates were not detected if the uterine cavity was scraped 3-4 months after IUD removal [9]. This allows us to assess the cellular infiltration of the endometrium during IUD use as a biological reaction of the organism to a foreign body. B.I. Zheleznov et al. [12] also believe that it is an expression of certain metabolic shifts in the organism and indicates a kind of immunological restructuring of the organism.

Chronic endometritis in the presence of IUD, according to the literature, occurs in 2-18 % [4]. At the same time H. Ludwig et al. on the basis of their observations came to the conclusion that the inflammatory process of the uterine mucosa detected in some women after IUD insertion is due to the incorrect selection of patients for this type of contraception. According to V.P. Emaykina et al. [1], focal endometritis occurs in 2.9-11.6% of women with IUDs, and in most cases the patients do not have gross morphological changes in the endometrium. Severe endometritis is not characteristic of women using IUDs [1, 3]. As for the incidence of chronic non-specific endometritis depending on the duration of intrauterine contraception, many authors have found an increase in the incidence of endometritis with an increase in the wearing of contraceptives for more than 4 - 5 years [2, 8]. V.G. Kaminskaya et al. [11] also indicate that after 6 to 7 years of IUD use, endometrial changes such as chronic endometritis are significant, and removal of the contraceptive is difficult. However, N.R. Safronnikova noted more frequent detection of chronic endometritis in the first 36 months of IUD use. In the opinion of B.I. Zhelezhnov and N.E. Loginova, when making a diagnosis of chronic endometritis, one should not attach great importance to any one sign, but should use their complex (inflammatory infiltrates consisting mainly of lymphoid and plasma cells, sclerotic changes in the walls of vessels, stromal fibrosis).

Atrophic changes of the endometrium (in 0.2-2.8 %) have been found in the sites of direct contact with the contraceptive during long-term intrauterine contraception [10].

Along with the data on reactive and inflammatory changes of the endometrium in response to the presence of a foreign body, there are indications of the possibility of glandular hyperplasia of the

endometrium in 2.3-8.9 % of patients. At the same time, these authors do not give an assessment of the hyperplastic processes detected by them, although, according to B.I. Zhelezhnov [4], it cannot be excluded that the concept of "glandular hyperplasias" includes atypical forms of them.

Y.A. Petrov established some features of hyperplastic changes in the uterine body mucosa in women using IUDs in the majority of observations glandular hyperplasias of the endometrium are asymptomatic, have the character of a mixed form, are usually transient and well amenable to therapy with hormonal contraceptives [5]. The obtained data confirm the results of other authors. Changes in the mitotic mode and decrease in the level of sex chromatin in the detected hyperplasias were moderate in nature, whereas the pre-cancerous processes of the endometrium are characterised by pronounced disturbances in the mitotic mode and a sharper decrease in the content of sex chromatin. Studies [2, 9] of the endometrium of young (up to 35 years of age) women who previously used IUDs indicate a reduced effect of progesterone on the endometrium, which may be one of the causes of glandular hyperplasias in women who do not suffer from pronounced neuroendocrine disorders. Some deficiency of the secretory phase of the menstrual cycle during IUD use is also noted by other authors [7]. It is necessary to take into account the data of a number of researchers indicating more frequent detection of anovulatory cycles in women using IUDs. Apparently, we should agree with the opinion of N.R. Safronnikova [9] that glandular hyperplasias in women with IUDs are a consequence of prolonged uncompensated relative hyperestrogenism as a result of anovulation. We should not forget that glandular hyperplasias of the endometrium can sometimes be observed in chronic endometritis [2, 3]. According to some researchers, the endometrial layer in contact with the IUD is rejected monthly during menstruation and replaced by a new one, so there is no prolonged contact of the intrauterine contraceptive device with the uterine mucosa, and, therefore, its malignancy is excluded. At the same time, cases of uterine mucosal cancer in women who have been wearing IUDs for a long time have been described in the literature. Southam [4, 6] reported the results of observation of 65 women who wore IUDs for 15 - 20 years, 401 patients who used them for 10 - 15 years, 442 women who used contraceptives for 5 - 10 years. None of them were found to have uterine cancer at systematic examination. The absence of a carcinogenic effect of IUDs on the endometrium has been noted by many authors [12].

Conclusions: Thus, most women with intrauterine contraception have a normal endometrial picture. Focal fibrosis of the stroma, lympholeukocytic infiltration, etc. detected in some observations can be considered a local reaction to the foreign body (IUD) and are temporary. Intrauterine contraception does not increase the incidence of atypical hyperplasia and endometrial cancer.

IQTIBOSLAR | ЧОККИ | REFERENCES:

1. Kuznetsova I. V. Modern intrauterine contraception // *Gynaecology*. 2012. T. 14. № 4. P. b2-b7.
2. Mukim-Zoda T. M., Pavlova I. P. Inflammatory diseases of the pelvic organs and long-term use of intrauterine contraception (clinical case) // *International Journal of Humanities and Natural Sciences*. 2019. № 1-1. C. 22-2B.
3. Mukhamedshina V. R., Sokolova T. M. Impact of contraception methods on women's reproductive health // *Siberian Medical Journal (Tomsk)*. 2014. T. 26. № 3-1. S. bb-B.
4. Prilepskaya V. N. Evolution of contraception in Russia // *Medical Opponent*. 201B. № 4. C. 16-21.
5. Malakhova A. A. Actual issues of the use of intrauterine contraceptives (literature review) // *Synergy of Sciences*. 2017. № 16. C. 755-770.
6. Ermakov A. N. Morphology of the uterine mucosa in the use of intrauterine contraceptives (literature review) // *International Journal of Experimental Education*. 2016. № 5-1. C. 59-62.
7. Petrov Yu. A. Assessment of adaptation and immune reserve of women with chronic endometritis depending on the amount of rehabilitation therapy // *Valeology*. 2016. № 2. C. 35-39.

8. Petrov Yu. A. The role of immune disorders in the genesis of chronic endometritis // Bulletin of Peoples' Friendship University of Russia. Series: Medicine. 2011. № 6. С. 2B2-2B9.
9. Davis H. IUD's Present Status and Future Prospects // Amer. J. Obstet. Gynec. 2012. No. 1. P. 134-151.
10. Moyer D. L. Reaction of human endometrium to the intrauterine foreign body. II. Long-term effects on the endometrial histology and cytology / D. L. Moyer, D. R. Mischel // Amer. J. Obstet. Gynec. 2014. No. 1. P. bb-B0.
11. Krasnopolsky V. I. I., Буянова S. N., Shchukina N. A. Purulent gynaecology. Moscow: MEDpress, 2013. 2BB p.
12. Shakhanova S. et al. MELANOMA OF THE SKIN AND PREGNANCY //Евразийский журнал академических исследований. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 120-128.
13. Zakhirova, N. N., Tillyashaykhov, M. N., Adylkhodjaev, A. A., Akhmedov, O. M., Osmanova, E. Z., Saydakhmedova, V. A., & Raximov, N. M. (2022). EXPERIENCE OF THE NATIONAL VACCINATION PROGRAM IMPLEMENTATION AGAINST HUMAN PAPILLOMA VIRUS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *World Bulletin of Public Health*, 13, 126-131.
14. Jasur Rizayev Alimjanovich, Larisa Rubenovna Agababyan, Anvar Ibragimovich Kamalov. AYOLLARDA TUG'RUQDAN KEYINGI QON KETISHLARNI OLDINI OLISH VA ULARGA QARSHI KURASHISH BO'YICHA KO'RSATILAYOTGAN XIZMATLAR SIFATINING MONITORINGINI TASHKIL ETISH// Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences Volume 1_ ISSUE 10, 2021 p. 166-169
15. Alimjanovich J. R., Agababyan L. R., Kamalov A. I. Prevention and Treatment of Postpartum Hemorrhage //CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 4. – С. 204-209.
16. 12. Intrauterine hormonal system: Issues of acceptability and safety / E. V. Ivanova, R. A. Sasunova, V. N. Letunovskaya, V. N. Prilepskaya, E. A. Mezhevitinova, A. V. Tagieva // Obstetrics and Gynaecology. 2011. № 4. С. 140-144.
17. Komarova V. S., Khlybova S. V. V., Zaitseva E. G. Course of inflammatory diseases of the pelvic organs against the background of long-term use of intrauterine contraceptives (case study) // Vyatka Medical Bulletin. 2015. № 3. С. 3.

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